

Generalization of Banach Fixed Point Theorem for T-Orbitally Complete Dislocated Metric Space

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 09 July 2024	Generalization of Banach Fixed Point Theorem for different metric spaces like dislocated metric space, dislocated quasi metric space, b-metric space and S-metric space etc was studied by several authors using different conditions on self-mapping. Dolhare and Nalawade studied the generalization in T -orbitally complete metric space. In this research article, we have proved two new results of the existence and uniqueness of fixed point for selfmapping in T -orbitally complete dislocated metric space by the rationalization condition on T . Also, we have proved consequences of our main results.
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INTRODUCTION AND PRELIMINARIES

The Banach fixed point theorem [1], which was published in 1922, is helpful in determining whether there are solutions to the various nonlinear issues that have arisen in the biological, physical, and social sciences, among other fields of study. Abramski and Jung [2] provided some information about

dislocated metric space in 1994. In 2000, Hitzler and Seda [3] introduced the idea of dislocated metric space, which provided some modifications to the Banach contraction principle in complete dislocated metric space. For similar results and some generalizations of Fixed Point Theorems, one can refer [5, 8, 10].

Definition 1.1 [6]. For the set $\mathcal{X} (\neq \emptyset)$ consider the map $d: \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ which satisfies:

$$(d_1) \quad d(x, y) = d(y, x) = 0 \implies x = y$$

$$(d_2) \quad d(x, y) = d(y, x), \forall x, y \in \mathcal{X}$$

$$(d_3) \quad d(x, y) \leq d(x, z) + d(z, y), \forall x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$$

Here d is called dislocated metric (DM) on \mathcal{X} and (\mathcal{X}, d) is called as a dislocated metric space (DMS).

Definition 1.2 [7]. In a DMS (\mathcal{X}, d) , sequence $\{x_n\}$ converges to z , if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x_n, z) =$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(z, x_n) = 0.$$

Definition 1.3 [7]. In a DMS (\mathcal{X}, d) , $\{x_n\}$ is said to be Cauchy if for a given $\epsilon > 0$, $\exists n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that, $\forall m, n \geq n_0$, $d(x_m, x_n) < \epsilon$.

Definition 1.4 [6]. A DMS (\mathcal{X}, d) is complete, if each Cauchy sequence in \mathcal{X} is convergent to a point in \mathcal{X} .

Definition 1.5 [4]. A function $\mathcal{T}: \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ is a λ -generalized contraction if and only if for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$ there are nonnegative numbers $p(x, y), q(x, y), r(x, y), s(x, y)$, such that

$$\sup_{x, y \in \mathcal{X}} \{p(x, y) + q(x, y) + r(x, y) + 2s(x, y)\} = \lambda < 1$$

and

$$d(\mathcal{T}x, \mathcal{T}y) \leq p(x, y)d(x, y) + q(x, y)d(x, \mathcal{T}x) + r(x, y)d(y, \mathcal{T}y) + s(x, y)[d(x, \mathcal{T}y) +$$

$d(y, \mathcal{T}x)$ holds for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$.

Definition 1.6 [4]. A space \mathcal{X} with a function $\mathcal{T}: \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ is called \mathcal{T} -orbitally complete metric space if every Cauchy sequence $\{\mathcal{T}^n x: i \in \mathbb{N}, x \in \mathcal{X}\}$ has a limit point in \mathcal{X} .

In next section, we generalize the results given by Nalavade in [9].

1. MAIN RESULTS

Theorem 2.1. For a T -Orbitally complete dislocated metric space (X, d) with self mapping $T: X \rightarrow X$, define an operation $*$ on X as $\alpha * x$, for $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ and $x \in X$ such that $\alpha * x \in \mathbb{R}$ and for any $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$, defined $d(\alpha x, \alpha y) = |\alpha|d(x, y)$. Also, for nonnegative numbers $p(x, y), q(x, y), r(x, y), s(x, y)$, which depends on x, y let there is a numbers $k \in \mathbb{R}^+$ with

$$\sup_{x,y \in X} (p(x, y) + q(x, y) + r(x, y) + 2s(x, y)) = \lambda < \frac{1}{k} \dots (1)$$

Define the function $\psi: X \rightarrow X$ as $\psi(x) = kx, k \in \mathbb{R}$, and T satisfies the condition

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq pd(\psi(x), \psi(y)) + q[d(\psi(x), \psi(Tx)) + d(\psi(y), \psi(Ty))] + r[d(\psi(x), \psi(Ty)) + d(\psi(y), \psi(Tx))] + s \left[\frac{d(\psi(x), \psi(Tx)) \cdot d(\psi(y), \psi(Ty))}{d(\psi(x), \psi(y))} \right] \dots (2)$$

for all $x, y \in X$. Then there exist unique $u \in T$ such that $T(u) = u$.

Proof. We will denote $\alpha * x$ by αx . Let $x_0 \in X$ be an arbitrary element and consider a sequence, $x_1 = Tx_0, x_2 = Tx_1, \dots, x_{n+1} = Tx_n, \dots$. Now by using the equation (2) and triangle inequality, gives

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_n, x_{n+1}) &= d(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_n) \\ &\leq pd(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(x_n)) + q[d(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(Tx_{n-1})) + d(\psi(x_n), \psi(Tx_n))] + r[d(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(Tx_n)) + d(\psi(x_n), \psi(Tx_{n-1}))] + \\ &\quad s \left[\frac{d(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(Tx_{n-1})) \cdot d(\psi(x_n), \psi(Tx_n))}{d(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(x_n))} \right] \\ &\leq pd(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(x_n)) + q[d(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(x_n)) + d(\psi(x_n), \psi(x_{n+1}))] + r[d(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(x_{n+1})) + d(\psi(x_n), \psi(x_n))] + \\ &\quad s \left[\frac{d(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(x_n)) \cdot d(\psi(x_n), \psi(x_{n+1}))}{d(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(x_n))} \right] \\ &\leq pkd(x_{n-1}, x_n) + qk[d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})] + rk[d(x_{n-1}, x_{n+1}) + d(x_n, x_n)] + ks[d(x_n, x_{n+1})] \\ &\leq pkd(x_{n-1}, x_n) + qk[d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})] + rk[d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + d(x_n, x_{n+1}) + d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})] + ks[d(x_n, x_{n+1})] \text{ which gives,} \\ &\quad (1 - qk - 2rk - ks)d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq (pk + qk + 2rk)d(x_{n-1}, x_n) \\ &\quad \text{i.e., } \Rightarrow d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq \left[\frac{p+q+2r}{\frac{1}{k}-q-2r-s} \right] d(x_{n-1}, x_n) \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq R d(x_{n-1}, x_n), \text{ where } R = \frac{p+q+2r}{\frac{1}{k}-q-2r-s} < 1 \text{ (by condition (1) in the theorem).}$$

k
In general, $d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq R^n d(x_0, x_1) \dots (3)$

Taking limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$, as $R < 1$, so $R^n \rightarrow 0$ and therefore from equation (3), we have $d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \rightarrow 0$.

This shows that, $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in a complete dislocated metric space (X, d) .

Therefore there exists $u \in X$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} T^n x_0 = u$. $\dots (4)$ Now, we will show that this u

is a fixed point of T .

Using equations (1) and (2) in the theorem 2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tu, Tx_n) &\leq pd(\psi(u), \psi(x_n)) + q[d(\psi(u), \psi(Tu)) + d(\psi(x_n), \psi(Tx_n))] \\ &\quad + r[d(\psi(u), \psi(Tx_n)) + d(\psi(x_n), \psi(Tu))] + s \left[\frac{d(\psi(u), \psi(Tu)) \cdot d(\psi(x_n), \psi(Tx_n))}{d(\psi(u), \psi(x_n))} \right] \\ &\leq pkd(u, x_n) + qk[d(u, Tu) + d(x_n, Tx_n)] + rk[d(u, Tx_n) + d(x_n, Tu)] \\ &\quad + sk \left[\frac{d(u, Tu) \cdot d(x_n, Tx_n)}{d(u, x_n)} \right] \end{aligned}$$

which gives,

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tu, Tx_n) &\leq pkd(u, x_n) + qk[d(u, Tu) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})] + rk[d(u, x_{n+1}) + d(x_n, Tu)] \\ &\quad + sk \left[\frac{d(u, Tu) \cdot d(x_n, x_{n+1})}{d(u, x_n)} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq pkd(u, x_n) + qk[d(u, x_{n+1}) + d(x_{n+1}, Tu) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})] \\ &\quad + rk[d(u, x_{n+1}) + d(x_n, Tu)] + sk \left[\frac{d(u, Tu) \cdot d(x_n, x_{n+1})}{d(u, x_n)} \right] \\ &\leq pkd(u, x_n) + qkd(u, x_{n+1}) + qkd(Tx_n, Tu) + qkd(x_n, x_{n+1}) \\ &\quad + rk d(u, x_{n+1}) + rk d(x_n, Tx_n) + rk d(Tx_n, Tu) + sk d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \left[\frac{d(u, Tu)}{d(u, x_n)} \right] \\ &\leq pkd(u, x_n) + qkd(u, x_{n+1}) + qkd(Tx_n, Tu) + qkd(x_n, x_{n+1}) \\ &\quad + rk d(u, x_{n+1}) + rk d(x_n, Tx_n) + rk d(Tx_n, Tu) + sk d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \left[\frac{d(u, Tx_n)}{d(u, x_n)} \right] \\ &\leq pkd(u, x_n) + (qk + rk)d(u, x_{n+1}) + (qk + rk + sk)d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \\ &\quad + (qk + rk)d(Tx_n, Tu) \\ &\leq \lambda d(u, x_n) + \lambda d(u, x_{n+1}) + \lambda d(x_n, x_{n+1}) + \lambda d(Tx_n, Tu) \\ &\quad (1 - \lambda)d(Tu, Tx_n) \leq \lambda [d(u, x_n) + d(u, x_{n+1}) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})] \\ \therefore d(Tu, Tx_n) &\leq \frac{\lambda}{1-\lambda} [d(u, x_n) + d(u, x_{n+1}) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})] \\ \text{Therefore, } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(Tu, Tx_n) &\leq \frac{\lambda}{1-\lambda} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} [d(u, x_n) + d(u, x_{n+1}) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})] \end{aligned}$$

By using equation (4) and that $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} [d(u, x_n) + d(u, x_{n+1}) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})] &= 0. \text{ Hence} \\ Tu = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Tx_n &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_{n+1} = u \end{aligned}$$

Thus, u is a fixed point of T .

Uniqueness:

Suppose that u and v are two distinct fixed points T i.e., $u \neq v$ and $T(u) = u, T(v) = v$.

By equations (1) and (2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(u, v) = d(Tu, Tv) &\leq pd(\psi(u), \psi(v)) + q[d(\psi(u), \psi(Tu)) + d(\psi(v), \psi(Tv))] \\ &\quad + r[d(\psi(u), \psi(Tv)) + d(\psi(v), \psi(Tu))] + s \left[\frac{d(\psi(u), \psi(Tu)) \cdot d(\psi(v), \psi(Tv))}{d(\psi(u), \psi(v))} \right] \\ &\leq pkd(u, v) + qk[d(u, Tu) + d(v, Tv)] + rk[d(u, Tv) + d(v, Tu)] \\ &\quad + sk \left[\frac{d(u, Tu) \cdot d(v, Tv)}{d(u, v)} \right] \\ &\leq pkd(u, v) + qk[d(u, u) + d(v, v)] + rk[d(u, v) + d(v, u)] \\ &\quad + sk \left[\frac{d(u, u) \cdot d(v, v)}{d(u, v)} \right] \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $d(u, v) \leq pkd(u, v) + 2rkd(u, v)$

$$\leq (pk + 2rk)d(u, v) \leq \lambda d(u, v)$$

Thus, $(1 - \lambda)d(u, v) \leq 0$ i.e., $d(u, v) = 0 \Rightarrow u = v$, which is a contradiction to $u \neq v$.

Hence, T has a unique fixed point.

Example 1. For the metric space (X, d) where $X = [0, 5]$, define $d(x, y) = \max\{x, y\}$ for all $x, y \in X$. Here $d(\alpha x, \alpha y) = \max\{\alpha x, \alpha y\} = |\alpha| \max\{x, y\} = |\alpha|d(x, y)$ for all $x, y \in X$.

Define $T: X \rightarrow X$ as $Tx = \frac{3}{5}x, \forall x \in X$. Then (X, d) is a T -orbitally complete dislocated metric

space. For $k = \frac{1}{2}$, consider the numbers $p(x, y) = \frac{3}{5}, q(x, y) = \frac{1}{5}, r(x, y) = \frac{1}{5}, s(x, y) = \frac{1}{5}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } \sup_{x, y \in X = [0, 5]} \{p(x, y) + q(x, y) + r(x, y) + 2s(x, y)\} &= \sup_{x, y \in X = [0, 5]} \left\{ \frac{3}{5} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{5} + 2 \cdot \frac{1}{5} \right\} \\ &= \frac{7}{5} = 1.4 < 2 = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{1}{k} \end{aligned}$$

Define the function $\psi: X \rightarrow X$ by $\psi(x) = kx, \forall x \in X$.

We have, $d(Tx, Ty) = d\left(\frac{3}{5}x, \frac{3}{5}y\right) = \max\left\{\frac{3}{5}x, \frac{3}{5}y\right\} = \frac{3}{5} \max\{x, y\} = \frac{3}{5}x$ or $\frac{3}{5}y$ and $pd(\psi(x), \psi(y)) + q[d(\psi(x), \psi(Tx)) + d(\psi(y), \psi(Ty))]$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & +r[d(\psi(x), \psi(Ty)) + d(\psi(y), \psi(Tx))] + s \left[\frac{d(\psi(x), \psi(Tx)) \cdot d(\psi(y), \psi(Ty))}{d(\psi(x), \psi(y))} \right] \\
 & = \frac{3}{5} d\left(\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{1}{2}y\right) + \frac{1}{5} \left[d\left(\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{3}{10}x\right) + d\left(\frac{1}{2}y, \frac{3}{10}y\right) \right] + \frac{1}{5} \left[d\left(\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{3}{10}y\right) + d\left(\frac{1}{2}y, \frac{3}{10}x\right) \right] + \\
 & \quad \frac{1}{5} \left[\frac{d\left(\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{3}{10}x\right) \cdot d\left(\frac{1}{2}y, \frac{3}{10}y\right)}{d\left(\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{1}{2}y\right)} \right] \\
 & = \frac{3}{5} \max\left\{\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{1}{2}y\right\} + \frac{1}{5} \left[\max\left\{\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{3}{10}x\right\} + \max\left\{\frac{1}{2}y, \frac{3}{10}y\right\} \right] + \frac{1}{5} \left[\max\left\{\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{3}{10}y\right\} + \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \max\left\{\frac{1}{2}y, \frac{3}{10}x\right\} \right] + \frac{1}{5} \left[\frac{\max\left\{\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{3}{10}x\right\} \cdot \max\left\{\frac{1}{2}y, \frac{3}{10}y\right\}}{\max\left\{\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{1}{2}y\right\}} \right] \\
 & = \frac{3}{5} \frac{1}{2} \max\{x, y\} + \frac{1}{10} \left[\max\left\{x, \frac{3}{5}x\right\} + \max\left\{y, \frac{3}{5}y\right\} \right] + \frac{1}{10} \left[\max\left\{x, \frac{3}{5}y\right\} + \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \max\left\{y, \frac{3}{5}x\right\} \right] + \frac{1}{10} \left[\frac{\max\left\{x, \frac{3}{5}x\right\} \cdot \max\left\{y, \frac{3}{5}y\right\}}{\max\{x, y\}} \right] \\
 & = \frac{3}{10}x + \frac{1}{10}[x + y] + \frac{1}{10}[x + y] + \frac{1}{10} \left[\frac{x \cdot y}{x} \right] \\
 & = \frac{3}{10}x + \frac{2}{10}x + \frac{2}{10}y + \frac{1}{10}y \\
 & = \frac{1}{2}x + \frac{3}{10}y
 \end{aligned}$$

OR

$$\begin{aligned}
 & = \frac{3}{10}y + \frac{1}{10}[x + y] + \frac{1}{10}[x + y] + \frac{1}{10} \left[\frac{x \cdot y}{y} \right] \\
 & = \frac{3}{10}y + \frac{2}{10}x + \frac{2}{10}y + \frac{1}{10}x \\
 & = \frac{1}{2}y + \frac{3}{10}x
 \end{aligned}$$

All the conditions of theorem 2.1 are satisfied here. Also $x = 0 \in X$ is the only fixed point of T .

Theorem 2.2. For a T -Orbitally complete dislocated metric space (X, d) with self mapping $T: X \rightarrow X$, define an operation $*$ on X as $\alpha * x$, for $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ and $x \in X$ such that $\alpha * x \in \mathbb{R}$ and for any $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$, define $d(\alpha x, \alpha y) = |\alpha|d(x, y)$. Also, for nonnegative numbers $p(x, y), q(x, y), r(x, y), s(x, y)$, which depends on x, y let there is a numbers $k \in \mathbb{R}^+$ with

$$\sup_{x, y \in X} (p(x, y) + q(x, y) + r(x, y) + 2s(x, y)) = \lambda < \frac{1}{k} \quad \dots(5)$$

Define the function $\psi: X \rightarrow X$ as $\psi(x) = kx, k \in \mathbb{R}$, and T satisfies the condition

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(Tx, Ty) & \leq pd(\psi(x), \psi(y)) + q[d(\psi(x), \psi(Tx)) + d(\psi(y), \psi(Ty))] \\
 & \quad + r[d(\psi(x), \psi(Ty)) + d(\psi(y), \psi(Tx))] + \\
 & \quad s \left[\frac{d(\psi(y), \psi(Ty)) [1 + d(\psi(x), \psi(Tx))]}{1 + d(\psi(x), \psi(y))} \right] \quad \dots(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

for all $x, y \in X$. Then there exist unique $u \in T$ such that $T(u) = u$.

Proof. We will denote $\alpha * x$ by αx . Let $x_0 \in X$ be an arbitrary element and consider a sequence, $x_1 = Tx_0, x_2 = Tx_1, \dots, x_{n+1} = Tx_n, \dots$. Now by using the equation (2) and triangle inequality, gives

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(x_n, x_{n+1}) & = d(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_n) \\
 & \leq pd(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(x_n)) + q[d(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(Tx_{n-1})) + d(\psi(x_n), \psi(Tx_n))] + r[d(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(Tx_n)) + d(\psi(x_n), \psi(Tx_{n-1}))] + \\
 & \quad s \left[\frac{d(\psi(x_n), \psi(Tx_n)) [1 + d(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(Tx_{n-1}))]}{1 + d(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(x_n))} \right] \\
 & \leq pd(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(x_n)) + q[d(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(x_n)) + d(\psi(x_n), \psi(x_{n+1}))] + r[d(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(x_{n+1})) + d(\psi(x_n), \psi(x_{n+1}))] + \\
 & \quad s \left[\frac{d(\psi(x_n), \psi(x_{n+1})) [1 + d(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(x_n))]}{1 + d(\psi(x_{n-1}), \psi(x_n))} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq pkd(x_{n-1}, x_n) + qk [d(x_{n-1}, Tx_{n-1}) + d(x_n, Tx_n)] + rk[d(x_{n-1}, Tx_n) + \\ &\quad d(x_n, Tx_{n-1})] + ks \left[\frac{d(x_n, Tx_n)[1+d(x_{n-1}, Tx_{n-1})]}{1+d(x_{n-1}, x_n)} \right] \\ &\leq pkd(x_{n-1}, x_n) + qk[d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})] + rk[d(x_{n-1}, x_{n+1}) + \\ &\quad d(x_n, x_n)] + ks \left[\frac{d(x_n, x_{n+1})[1+d(x_{n-1}, x_n)]}{1+d(x_{n-1}, x_n)} \right] \\ &\leq pkd(x_{n-1}, x_n) + qk[d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})] + rk[d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + \\ &\quad d(x_n, x_{n+1}) + d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})] + ks[d(x_n, x_{n+1})] \end{aligned}$$

which gives,

$$\begin{aligned} (1 - qk - 2rk - ks)d(x_n, x_{n+1}) &\leq (pk + qk + 2rk)d(x_{n-1}, x_n) \\ \text{i.e., } \Rightarrow d(x_n, x_{n+1}) &\leq \left[\frac{pk+qk+2rk}{1-qk-2rk-ks} \right] d(x_{n-1}, x_n) \\ \Rightarrow d(x_n, x_{n+1}) &\leq \left[\frac{p+q+2r}{\frac{1}{k}-q-2r-s} \right] d(x_{n-1}, x_n) \\ \Rightarrow d(x_n, x_{n+1}) &\leq R d(x_{n-1}, x_n), \text{ where } R = \frac{p+q+2r}{\frac{1}{k}-q-2r-s} < 1 \end{aligned}$$

$\overset{k}{k}$
(by condition (5) in the theorem 2.2).

In general, $d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq R^n d(x_0, x_1)$... (7)

Taking limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$, as $R < 1$, so $R^n \rightarrow 0$ and therefore from equation (7), we have $d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \rightarrow 0$.

This shows that, $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in a complete dislocated metric space (X, d) .

Therefore there exists $u \in X$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} T^n x_0 = u$... (8) Now, we will show that this u is a fixed point of T

Using equations (5) and (6) in the theorem 2.2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tu, Tx_n) &\leq pd(\psi(u), \psi(x_n)) + q[d(\psi(u), \psi(Tu)) + d(\psi(x_n), \psi(Tx_n))] \\ &\quad + r[d(\psi(u), \psi(Tx_n)) + d(\psi(x_n), \psi(Tu))] \\ &\quad + s \left[\frac{d(\psi(x_n), \psi(Tx_n))[1+d(\psi(u), \psi(Tu))]}{1+d(\psi(u), \psi(x_n))} \right] \\ &\leq pkd(u, x_n) + qk[d(u, Tu) + d(x_n, Tx_n)] + rk[d(u, Tx_n) + d(x_n, Tu)] \\ &\quad + sk \left[\frac{d(x_n, Tx_n)[1+d(u, Tu)]}{1+d(u, x_n)} \right] \end{aligned}$$

which gives,

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tu, Tx_n) &\leq pkd(u, x_n) + qk[d(u, Tu) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})] + rk[d(u, x_{n+1}) + d(x_n, Tu)] \\ &\quad + sk \left[\frac{d(x_n, x_{n+1})[1+d(u, Tu)]}{1+d(u, x_n)} \right] \\ &\leq pkd(u, x_n) + qkd(u, x_{n+1}) + qkd(x_{n+1}, Tu) + qkd(x_n, x_{n+1}) \\ &\quad + rkd(u, x_{n+1}) + rkd(x_n, x_{n+1}) + rkd(x_{n+1}, Tu) + \\ &\quad + sk \left[\frac{d(x_n, x_{n+1})[1+d(u, x_n)]}{1+d(u, x_n)} \right] \\ &\leq pkd(u, x_n) + (qk + rk)d(u, x_{n+1}) + (qk + rk + sk)d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \\ &\quad + (qk + rk)d(Tx_n, Tu) \\ &\leq \lambda d(u, x_n) + \lambda d(u, x_{n+1}) + \lambda d(x_n, x_{n+1}) + \lambda d(Tx_n, Tu) \\ (1 - \lambda)d(Tu, Tx_n) &\leq \lambda [d(u, x_n) + d(u, x_{n+1}) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})] \\ \therefore d(Tu, Tx_n) &\leq \frac{\lambda}{1-\lambda} [d(u, x_n) + d(u, x_{n+1}) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})] \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(Tu, Tx_n) \leq \frac{\lambda}{1-\lambda} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} [d(u, x_n) + d(u, x_{n+1}) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})]$

By using equation (8) and that $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} [d(u, x_n) + d(u, x_{n+1}) + d(x_n, x_{n+1})] &= 0. \text{ Hence} \\ Tu = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Tx_n &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_{n+1} = u \end{aligned}$$

Thus, u is a fixed point of T .

Uniqueness:

Suppose that u and v are two distinct fixed points T i.e., $u \neq v$ and $T(u) = u, T(v) = v$.

By equations (1) and (2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(u, v) &= d(Tu, Tv) \leq pd(\psi(u), \psi(v)) + q[d(\psi(u), \psi(Tu)) + d(\psi(v), \psi(Tv))] \\ &\quad + r[d(\psi(u), \psi(Tv)) + d(\psi(v), \psi(Tu))] + s \left[\frac{d(\psi(v), \psi(Tv))[1+d(\psi(u), \psi(Tu))]}{1+d(\psi(u), \psi(v))} \right] \\ &\leq pkd(u, v) + qk[d(u, Tu) + d(v, Tv)] + rk[d(u, Tv) + d(v, Tu)] \\ &\quad + sk \left[\frac{d(v, Tv)[1+d(u, Tu)]}{1+d(u, v)} \right] \\ &\leq pkd(u, v) + qk[d(u, u) + d(v, v)] + rk[d(u, v) + d(v, u)] \\ &\quad + sk \left[\frac{d(v, v)[1+d(u, u)]}{1+d(u, v)} \right] \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $d(u, v) \leq pkd(u, v) + 2rkd(u, v)$

$$\leq (pk + 2rk)d(u, v) \leq \lambda d(u, v)$$

Thus, $(1 - \lambda)d(u, v) \leq 0$ i.e., $d(u, v) = 0 \Rightarrow u = v$, which is a contradiction to $u \neq v$.

Hence, T has a unique fixed point.

Example 2. For the metric space (X, d) , where $X = [0, 6]$, define $d(x, y) = \max\{x, y\}$ for all $x, y \in X$. Here $d(\alpha x, \alpha y) = \max\{\alpha x, \alpha y\} = |\alpha| \max\{x, y\} = |\alpha|d(x, y)$ for all $x, y \in X$.

Define $T: X \rightarrow X$ as $Tx = \frac{4}{5}x, \forall x \in X$. Then (X, d) is a T -orbitally complete dislocated metric

space. For $k = \frac{1}{2}$, consider the numbers $p(x, y) = \frac{3}{5}, q(x, y) = \frac{1}{5}, r(x, y) = \frac{2}{5}, s(x, y) = \frac{1}{5}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } \sup_{\substack{X \\ [0, 6]}} \{p(x, y) + q(x, y) + r(x, y) + 2s(x, y)\} &= \sup_{x, y \in X = [0, 5]} \left\{ \frac{3}{5} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{2}{5} + 2 \cdot \frac{1}{5} \right\} \\ x, y \in &= \frac{8}{5} = 1.6 < 2 = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{1}{k} \end{aligned}$$

2

Define the function $\psi: X \rightarrow X$ by $\psi(x) = kx, \forall x \in X$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{We have, } d(Tx, Ty) &= d\left(\frac{4}{5}x, \frac{4}{5}y\right) = \max\left\{\frac{4}{5}x, \frac{4}{5}y\right\} = \frac{4}{5} \max\{x, y\} = \frac{4}{5}x \text{ or } \frac{4}{5}y \text{ and} \\ &\quad pd(\psi(x), \psi(y)) + q[d(\psi(x), \psi(Tx)) + d(\psi(y), \psi(Ty))] \\ &\quad + r[d(\psi(x), \psi(Ty)) + d(\psi(y), \psi(Tx))] + s \left[\frac{d(\psi(y), \psi(Ty))[1+d(\psi(x), \psi(Tx))]}{1+d(\psi(x), \psi(y))} \right] \\ &= \frac{3}{5}d\left(\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{1}{2}y\right) + \frac{1}{5} \left[d\left(\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{4}{10}x\right) + d\left(\frac{1}{2}y, \frac{4}{10}y\right) \right] + \frac{2}{5} \left[d\left(\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{4}{10}y\right) + d\left(\frac{1}{2}y, \frac{4}{10}x\right) \right] + \\ &\quad \frac{1}{5} \left[\frac{d\left(\frac{1}{2}y, \frac{4}{10}y\right)[1+d\left(\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{4}{10}x\right)]}{1+d\left(\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{1}{2}y\right)} \right] \\ &= \frac{3}{5} \max\left\{\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{1}{2}y\right\} + \frac{1}{5} \left[\max\left\{\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{4}{10}x\right\} + \max\left\{\frac{1}{2}y, \frac{4}{10}y\right\} \right] + \frac{2}{5} \left[\max\left\{\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{4}{10}y\right\} + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \max\left\{\frac{1}{2}y, \frac{4}{10}x\right\} \right] + \frac{1}{5} \left[\frac{\max\left\{\frac{1}{2}y, \frac{4}{10}y\right\}[1+\max\left\{\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{4}{10}x\right\}]}{1+\max\left\{\frac{1}{2}x, \frac{1}{2}y\right\}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

Case 1: If $x > y$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{3}{5} \frac{1}{2}x + \frac{1}{5} \left[\frac{1}{2}x + \frac{1}{2}y \right] + \frac{2}{5} \left[\frac{1}{2}x + \frac{1}{2}y \right] + \frac{1}{5} \left[\frac{\frac{1}{2}y[1+\frac{1}{2}x]}{1+\frac{1}{2}x} \right] \\ &= \frac{3}{10}x + \frac{1}{10}[x + y] + \frac{1}{5}[x + y] + \frac{1}{10}y \\ &= \left(\frac{3}{10} + \frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{5}\right)x + \left(\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{10}\right)y \\ &= \frac{3}{5}x + \frac{2}{10}y \end{aligned}$$

Case 2: If $y > x$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{3}{5} \frac{1}{2} y + \frac{1}{5} \left[\frac{1}{2} x + \frac{1}{2} y \right] + \frac{2}{5} \left[\frac{1}{5} x + \frac{1}{2} y \right] + \frac{1}{5} \left[\frac{\frac{1}{2} y \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} x \right]}{1 + \frac{1}{2} y} \right] \\
 &= \frac{3}{10} y + \frac{1}{10} [x + y] + \frac{2}{10} x + \frac{2}{10} y + \frac{1}{10} \left[\frac{y + \frac{1}{2} xy}{1 + \frac{1}{2} y} \right] \\
 &= \frac{3}{5} y + \frac{3}{10} x + \frac{1}{10} \left[\frac{y + \frac{1}{2} xy}{1 + \frac{1}{2} y} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

All the conditions of theorem 2.1 are satisfied here. Also $x = 0 \in X$ is the only fixed point of T .

CONCLUSION

In this research article, we have proved two new results of the existence and uniqueness of fixed point with examples for surjective self-mapping in complete dislocated metric space. Also, we have proved consequences on our main results and generalizes some well-known similar results in the literature of fixed point theory.

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